

Tracing Out the Neutrino Sky with TAMBO

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JOHN
TEMPLETON
FOUNDATION

TAMBO will:

Discover new point sources of neutrinos

Probe nature of diffuse flux from 1-100 PeV

Explore ultra-high energy flavor physics

Bridging the gap between HE & UHE ν observatories

← IceCube, KM3NeT, P-ONE,
Baikal-GVD & many proposals

→ GRAND, BEACON, PUEO,
RNO-G & more

- Community has heeded call for UHE neutrino observatories
 - But fewer experiments planned for 1-100 PeV
 - Notably TAMBO and TRINITY
- Explores cosmogenic flux models that peak at PeV energies

Recent result: IceCube 12.6 yr EHE
[PRL 135 031001 \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.1001)

Where are point sources hiding?

Adapted from: IceCube, Nature **378**, 6619 (2022)

Look-elsewhere effect hampers discovery of neutrino sources
 TAMBO will create a neutrino catalog with up to $2 \nu_\tau$ per year

What is the flavor of the high-energy Universe?

In-ice radio & radar

ν_τ -specific observatories

Combined

ν_τ -specific observatories are necessary to resolve >100 PeV flavor composition!

- Detect air shower particles on the side of a canyon
 - High astro purity from ν_τ exclusivity
 - Low cosmic ray backgrounds due to canyon shielding
 - $<1^\circ$ angular resolution
 - Proven detector technology in air shower arrays
 - Baseline design: 5000 modules, 150m spacing
- Expect to observe $\sim 1-3 \nu_\tau/\text{yr}$

1-3 ν_τ will:

Discover new point sources of neutrinos

Probe nature of diffuse flux from 1-100 PeV

Explore ultra-high energy flavor physics

AIR SHOWER:
3 - 10 KM LENGTH
200 M DIAMETER

DECAY

RANGE:
50 M - 5 KM

CHARGED-CURRENT
INTERACTION

~150 M
SEPARATION

AIR SHOWER
DETECTOR ARRAY
~M² EACH

ROCK

> 4 KM SHIELDING FROM
BACKGROUND MUONS

DEEP VALLEY

TAU AIR-SHOWER MOUNTAIN-BASED OBSERVATORY (TAMBO)

ν_τ exclusivity \rightarrow high astro purity

Air showers overwhelmingly come from ν_τ
 + atmospheric flux nearly 0% ν_τ

\therefore air shower is smoking-gun signal of astrophysical neutrino!

Observatory Location

Canyon	Depth (m)	Width (km)	Location and Notes
Yarlung Tsangpo Canyon	~6000	~5–10	Tibet; extremely deep but very remote.
Cotahuasi Canyon	3535	~3	Peru; deep and accessible.
Colca Canyon	3270	~4–5	Peru; deep and accessible.
Kali Gandaki Gorge	~2500	~5	Nepal; very deep but narrow and remote.
Hells Canyon	~2440	~16	USA (Oregon–Idaho); deepest river gorge in North America with steep walls.
Grand Canyon	~1800	~16	USA (Arizona); massive volume and excellent infrastructure.
Tara River Canyon	~1300	~3	Montenegro/Bosnia; Europe's deepest.

Location will determine sky coverage, detection efficiency, and background rejection

In what follows I will show results for the Colca Valley Location

The final location of TAMBO is still under consideration and will be decided based on a combination of scientific, logistical, and societal considerations

Humanities can help make physics greener, J de Swart, AC Thresher, CA Argüelles, *Nature Reviews Physics* 6 (7), 404-405

TAMBO Collaboration, arXiv:2507.08070

Benchmark studies include 5000 modules

- 150 meter spacing on triangular grid \rightarrow ~ 33 (16.5) km along and 3km up canyon if single- (double-) sided

Example ν_τ Event

Why put a neutrino telescope in a canyon?

Inherently low geometrical acceptance

Why put a neutrino telescope in a canyon?

Better for physics, but the engineers didn't seem to like it

Why put a neutrino telescope in a canyon?

We'll do this instead

Why put a neutrino telescope in a canyon?

**not to scale*

Mountain-through-going event
(~downgoing/horizontal)

Earth-skimming event
(~upgoing)

A canyon enhances our sky coverage

Downgoing

Upgoing

Full acceptance

Acceptance increased by $\sim 50\%$ compared with Earth-skimming only

And blocks cosmic-ray backgrounds

TAMBO's ν_τ sensitivity surpasses large-volume observatories

5x higher ν_τ aperture than IceCube at 10 PeV, before array optimization

Sources of events in TAMBO

With 5000 modules TAMBO will:

- Observe ~ 1 neutrino per year assuming just IceCube SPL flux
- Optimistic source¹ & cosmogenic fluxes² $\rightarrow \sim 2$ per year, observe cosmogenic flux

Enter TAMBITO

- 100-detector prototype for:
 - Detection unit R&D
 - Deployment tests
 - CR air shower measurements
- Initiate community outreach program
- Fully funded; development began in August!

Core component of TAMBITO: responsible siting

- Want local community to embrace project, not just accept
- First step: workshop in January 2024
- Success story: Pierre Auger

[Pierre Auger, ICRC 2025](#)

PIERRE
AUGER
OBSERVATORY

Thanks to U. Wisconsin & KIT for detector supplies!

TAMBO timeline

Today:
TAMBO-4

Small test array

Detector & electronics prototypes

2025-2028:
TAMBITO (TAMBO-100)

FUNDED!

Pilot array

Deployment techniques,
backgrounds, responsible siting

2028-:
TAMBO-5k

Target full size array

Thanks!

CIFAR

+

=

Le Verrier, 1846

+

=

Quanta Magazine

Why Neutrino Astronomy?

- Neutrinos are:
 - (Very) weakly interacting
 - Electrically neutral
- They also:
 - Can pass through dense areas of space unimpeded
 - Are not bent by magnetic fields
- But also makes them difficult to detect; enormous detectors

Image Credit: IceCube Collaboration/WIPAC, Juan Antonio Aguilar, and Jamie Yang.

Next-Generation Prospects

Diffuse Flux, 1:1:1 Flavor Ratio

- Community has heeded call for UHE neutrino observatories
 - But fewer experiments planned for 1-100 PeV
- TAMBO bridges the gap between HE & UHE observatories
 - Sensitive from ~300 TeV to ≥ 1 EeV

NOTE
PROJECTS MARKED IN **BLUE** ARE COMPLETE OR UNDER CONSTRUCTION.
PROJECTS MARKED IN **WHITE** ARE PROPOSED.

Will Thompson - TeVPA 20

- Mountain acts as filter for muon backgrounds
- Neutrino purity tunable based on column depth requirement

- Complementary flavor measurements with IceCube-style detectors
- High-purity astrophysical neutrino sample
 - Astrophysical flux dominates $\gtrsim 100$ TeV
 - Atmospheric flux is τ -poor

Air-Shower Simulation

- CORSIKA8 tracks individual particle energies & arrival times
- Enables in-depth rate & reconstruction studies

Taking Advantage of Tau Regeneration

Safa et al., JCAP 01 012 (2020)

Developing Full Simulation

Preliminary Simulation

Updated Simulation

- Simplified geometry
- No treatment of τ energy losses
- Approximation of air shower physics

- Realistic geometry
- Full treatment of τ energy losses
- Air shower simulation with CORSIKA 8

Developing Full Simulation

Preliminary Simulation

Jeff Lazar

Updated Simulation

Pavel Zhelnin

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The Canyon is an Astrophysical ν_τ Sieve

- Air-shower is exclusive to ν_τ
- μ^- energy greatly attenuated
- e^- entirely shielded by rock

Air-Shower Simulation

- CORSIKA8 tracks individual particle energies & arrival times
- Enables in-depth rate & reconstruction studies

Cella Cella

rani

Mismi

Huarancante

Chivay

Tapay

Cabanaconde

Taking Advantage of Tau Regeneration

[J. Lazar & P. Zhelnin PoS\(ICRC2023\)11117](#)

- Incoming ν_{τ} can undergo several $\nu_{\tau} \leftrightarrow \tau$ conversions in the Earth
- Results in higher rates than predicted by preliminary simulation
- Updated simulation handles tau regeneration via TauRunner¹

¹Safa *et al.*, CPC **278 108422** (2022)

Peru Outreach Trip

Photo Credit: Universidad Nacional de San Agustin de Arequipa

- Traveled to Peru in fall 2022 to meet with officials and visit site

TAMBO & the Canyon

Most promising location quite remote; closer areas for test array

TAMBO Is Complementary to High-Statistics Observatories

- Sensitive to source scenario of KM3NeT flux
- Instantaneous and integrated sky coverage overlaps with Cherenkov telescopes

- All-sky searches penalized by large trials factors:

~445,000 trials

→ 19.8 trials per square degree

- TAMBO's neutrino catalog with greatly reduce these trials factors

TAMBO Hardware Requirements

- 1° pointing resolution → O(ns) timing
- Ease of deployment on canyon face → water Cherenkov vs plastic scintillator
- Reduce wiring → wireless communication
- Low ecological footprint
- Affordable

Pierre Auger Observatory: a success story

3,000 km² observatory in Argentina with:

- Responsible land use agreements with 400+ landowners
- New power lines & internet
- Organized local science fairs
- Competition to name detectors in local schools
- Visitor center open 7 day/week
- Public talks

[Pierre Auger Collaboration, ICRC 2017](#)

KM3NeT Very High Energy Event

Neutrino Flux Models

